

laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Three seeds/hill were dibbled in May at 15- × 10-cm row spacing for semidry conditions and three seedling/hill were transplanted in July at 15- × 10-cm spacing for wet conditions. Fertilizer was applied at 75-37.5-37.5 kg NPK/ha.

TP-AS42673 (ASD/IR36) gave the highest mean grain yield under both conditions (see table). Its higher yield potential may be ascribed to more productive tillers and more grains/panicle.

TP-AS42673 is a semidwarf variety with high tillering ability and light green foliage. The panicle is compact with good spikelet fertility. Grain is short bold, with a white pericarp. It shows tolerance for drought and blast. ■

Performance of TP-AS42673 under semidry and wet conditions at Agricultural Research Station, Thirupathisaram, Tamil Nadu, India.

Entry	Parentage	Grain yield (t/ha)						Overall mean	Productive tillers/hill (no.)	Grains/panicle (no.)
		Semidry			Wet					
		1989	1990	Mean	1989	1990	Mean			
TP-AS42673	ASD8/IR36	4.6	4.7	4.6	5.0	4.6	4.8	4.7	10	202
TP-AS26556	IET5233/IR2153	5.3	4.5	4.9	2.9	3.8	3.3	4.1	10	179
TP-AS22954	IRON309/ADT31	4.9	4.2	4.5	3.8	3.9	3.8	4.1	10	188
TP-AS42700	ASD8/IR50	4.2	4.1	4.1	4.2	4.0	4.1	4.1	8	178
TP-AS25370	ASD1/IRON297	2.8	3.9	3.3	4.6	4.5	4.5	4.0	7	174
TP-AS42698	ASD8/IR36	4.4	3.5	3.9	3.8	4.2	4.0	4.0	8	152
TP-AS42692	ASD8/IR36	4.3	3.2	3.7	3.8	4.2	4.0	4.0	9	149
TP-AS37419	IET1444/IR20	3.8	3.3	3.5	4.0	3.1	3.5	3.6	7	128
TPS1 (check)	IR8/Kattisamba	5.1	4.1	4.6	3.6	3.9	3.7	4.1	8	178
TKM9 (check)	TKM7/IR8	4.2	3.5	3.8	3.3	4.2	3.7	3.6	8	162
	LSD (0.05)	1.1	0.2	0.7	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.5		

Integrated germplasm improvement—deepwater

Newly released deepwater rice varieties in West Bengal

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Four new rice varieties developed for deep water (50-100 cm) at the Chinsurah RRS were released in 1989.

NC490 (IET8987), released as Nalini, is a pureline selection from farmers' cultivar Sindurmukhi. It is photoperiod-sensitive and flowers 26-28 Oct in West Bengal. Well-exserted panicles are 22 cm long with about 200 medium slender grains (5.6 mm long, 2.5 L/B ratio); 1,000-grain weight is 20 g. Highest yield was 5.8 t/ha at Central Rice Research Institute (CRRI), Cuttack, in 1983 preliminary yield trials. Average yield was 3.4 t/ha (see table). Nalini is resistant to blast (Bl) and moderately resistant to stem borer (SB), sheath blight (ShB), and bacterial blight (BB).

NC491 (IET8988), released as Matangini, was selected from Kajallata. It flowers in late Oct. Its compact panicle has about 200 short bold grains (6 mm long, 2.0 L/B ratio); 1,000-grain weight is 27.2 g. It had the highest yield at CRRI, 6.6 t/ha in 1983. Matangini is

Yields of new deepwater rice varieties in state and national trials in India, 1983-88.

Year	Trial ^a	Sites (no.)	Water depth (cm)	Yield ^b (t/ha)	
				New variety	Check
<i>NC490 (IET8987), Nalini</i>					
1983	National (PVT-5)	7	42 - 75	3.6*	2.9 (Tilakkachari)
1984	National (UVT-5)	7	36 - 66	3.1	2.8 (Local variety)
1985	National (UVT-5)	10	22 - 90	3.0**	1.9 (Janki)
1985	Physiological screening	3		3.5*	2.8 (Local variety)
1986-88	State adaptive	4	50 - 85	3.1*	2.5 (Tilakkachari)
1988	On-farm (minikit) (3 districts)	8		3.9	
	Total or av	36		3.4	
<i>NC491 (IET8988), Matangini</i>					
1983	National (PVT-5)	3	42 - 65	3.8**	2.3 (Local variety)
1985	National (UVT-5)	9	22 - 90	3.0	2.7 (Local variety)
1985	Physiological screening	1		2.5	2.2 (Local variety)
1986	National (UVT-5)	3	62 - 110	2.5	2.1 (Local variety)
1986	Physiological screening	2		3.3*	2.8 (Local variety)
1986-88	State adaptive	5	65-100	3.4*	2.6 (NC487)
	Total or ave	23		3.1	
<i>NC493 (IET8989), Amulya</i>					
1983	National (PVT-5)	4	42 - 75	3.3	2.9 (Tilakkachari)
1984	National (UVT-5)	8	36 - 66	3.1*	2.5 (Local variety)
1985	National (UVT-5)	9	22 - 90	3.2**	2.0 (Janki)
1985	Physiological screening	4		3.6	3.2 (Local variety)
1987-88	State adaptive	2	55 - 95	3.0*	2.2 (NC488)
1988	On-farm (minikit) (3 districts)	8		3.1	
	Total or av	35		3.2	
<i>CN570-652-39-2 (IET10001), Dinesh</i>					
1985	National (PVT-5)	3	40 - 55	3.3*	2.7 (Tilakkachari)
1986	National (UVT-5)	4			1.9 (Local variety)
1986	Physiological screening	2	62 - 113	2.7*	1.9 (Janki)
1987	National (UVT-5)	5	50 - 108	4.5**	2.8 (Local variety)
				3.0*	2.2 (Local variety)
1987-88	National (UVT-6)	3	95 - 116	3.5**	2.4 (Local variety)
1987	Physiological screening	1		3.5	3.0 (NC492)
1987-88	State adaptive	2	75 - 105	3.3**	2.1 (Jaladhi 2)
	Total or av	20		3.4	

^aPVT-5 = preliminary variety trial-5, UVT-5 = uniform variety trial-5, UVT-6 = uniform variety trial-6. ^b*,** = significant at 5 and 1% level.

moderately resistant to B1 and ShB, and moderately susceptible to BB.

NC493 (IET8989), released as Amulya, is a selection from the land race Najani. It is photoperiod-sensitive and flowers 26-28 Oct. Panicles are long, compact, and well-exserted, with more than 200 long slender grains (6.4 mm

long, 3.1 L/B ratio); 1,000-grain weight is 24 g. Highest yield was 7.4 t/ha in uniform variety trials at Arundhutinagar, Tripura, in 1985. Amulya is resistant to ShB and moderately resistant to BB and SB.

CN570-652-39-2 (IET10001), released as Dinesh, is from a cross

between Jaladhi 2 and Pankaj. It flowers 30 Oct-3 Nov. It has good kneeing ability. Panicles are 22 cm long with 185 short bold grains (5.9 mm long, 2.0 L/B ratio). It had the highest yield (4.8 t/ha) at Chinsurah in 1987. It is moderately resistant to ShB and B1 and moderately susceptible to BB. ■

Seed technology

Hand-operated vacuum packing system for rice seed storage

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We developed a hand-operated vacuum packing system to facilitate dry seed storage. Reducing the oxygen content in sealed containers prevents seed rehydration and suffocates, adult insects. Components of the vacuum packing system are

- a bicycle tire pump, with pump plunger seal or cup in reverse, to use as the vacuum pump;
- a tire inner tube stem valve, to use as a check valve to prevent backflow of air into the vacuum chamber;
- a large food can, irrigation pipe, or pressure cooker to use as the vacuum chamber;

- a lid for the vacuum chamber, used with a rubber gasket made from a tire inner tube and sheet metal or wood;
- a glass jar with a screw cap and gasket or a lid with a plastic inner liner, to use as the storage container.

Seeds are placed in the glass jar and its lid is twisted on snugly, but not so tight that air cannot escape during evacuation. The jar is placed in the vacuum chamber, the chamber evacuated, and the vacuum released rapidly. The rapid intake of air into the vacuum chamber will slam the jar lid down and seal it. Tightening the screw cap will help secure the seal.

A vacuum system using a 16-cm-diameter × 17-cm-high food can requires 8-15 strokes with the modified (4-cm-diameter × 62-cm-high) bicycle pump to attain a vacuum adequate for sealing. We have easily achieved 50-80 kPa

Vacuum packing system: a) bicycle pump with reversed cup, b) tire stem valve, c) rubber stopper, d) sheet metal or plywood, e) rubber gasket, f) jar, and g) food can.

(15-25 inches mercury) suction. Larger vacuum chambers need more strokes to achieve the desired air evacuation.

Including dehydrating agents, such as silica gel, in the storage jar facilitates moisture control. ■

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Physiology and plant nutrition

Rice mitochondria surface membrane contains concanavalin A receptors

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Cell organoids membranes contain the residues of different sugars. The residues in surface membranes provide informational cooperation with other organoids, transport molecules, etc. The presence of sugar residue in the surface membrane of

1. Rice mitochondria stained with Con A gold conjugate suspension.

2. Rice mitochondria stained with Con A gold conjugate.